

Narcissistic (Personality Disorder) and Guilt

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Abstract

This article aims to examine the correlation between narcissism and emotions of guilt, as well as the distinctions in this connection between the sensitive and grandiose aspects of narcissism. Narcissistic personality disorder (NPD) is a psychological condition marked by an individual's inflated sense of self-importance, incessant pursuit of adulation, and absence of empathy. This illness may influence persons' perception and experience of guilt. Narcissistic persons often disregard the repercussions of their actions and evade accountability. Consequently, it is evident that those exhibiting narcissistic traits experience little or no guilt. This circumstance might engender difficulties in social connections and increase the individual's propensity to display detrimental behaviors. This research aims to elucidate the correlation between narcissistic personality disorder and guilt, while also investigating the social and psychological ramifications of this interplay.

The Narcissistic Personality Inventory (NPI) scale was used for this aim. A survey research was conducted in 2024 with the phrases narcissism, NPI (narcissistic personality disorder), and shame guilt. The relationship between narcissistic personality disorder and guilt was analyzed, along with the challenges faced in treatment methodologies stemming from these findings.

Keywords: *Narcissism, Personality Disorder, Guilt, Shame and Guilt*

Introduction

Interest in narcissistic personality disorder, the contemporary personality disorder, is growing daily. Following advancements in the study of personality disorders over the last three decades, Narcissistic Personality Disorder has surfaced as a novel domain for research and intervention (Schalkwijk et al., 2021). The interest in narcissistic personality disorders aligns with a recent trend in personality research.

Narcissistic personality disorder (NPD) is a multifaceted personality disorder that has garnered significant interest in the field of psychiatry. This disease is marked by notable traits like

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excessive self-admiration, a pursuit of superiority, a deficiency in empathy, and insensitivity to the needs of others.

Narcissistic Personality Disorder is characterized by an incessant self-admiration, both physically and spiritually, a perception of one's traits as exceptional, a lack of desire and awareness (empathy) to reciprocate interest towards others from whom admiration, appreciation, and approval are sought, and a propensity to invade and exploit (Akhtar, 2009). Narcissistic personality disorder may stem from early childhood experiences and parental attitudes. Excessive early attention or, alternatively, emotional deprivation might facilitate the development of narcissistic personality characteristics. Parents' excessive indulgence or harsh criticism might hinder a person from developing a healthy self-esteem. This may lead the person to perpetually seek external validation and recognition in later years.

He aspires to achieve perfection in several pursuits that he perceives as emblems of power. His most prominent trait is his pompous disposition. He diligently evades domains in which he is deficient and circumstances that induce feelings of worthlessness. He struggles to trust others.

They may have inflated expressions of affection rooted in emotional connections and assert that no one can love as they do; nonetheless, their capacity for love remains underdeveloped and they are incapable of genuine love. They believe they are the one who attracts the most attention and merits the most acclaim in social interactions and interpersonal communication, achieving achievement on a social level. They have acquired the capability to conceal circumstances in which they lack purpose. They exhibit enthusiasm, although transiently. They struggle to engage in an internal process that may serve as a foundation for their passion. Their capacity to endure or handle criticism or judgment is little. When individuals articulate their demands or insist on their fulfillment, their capacity to satisfy those needs is often diminished, or the desire they fulfill is to get affirmative sentiments replete with commendation directed towards themselves. Irrespective of the nature of the connections they build, their objective is self-aggrandizement. They may amend ethical regulations or the principles they uphold in matters of interest.

He/she may see differing opinions as an affront. He/she attempts to project an image of profundity, seeming intelligent; nevertheless, upon closer scrutiny, the insufficiency of his/her intellect and expertise becomes evident. Within this psychological construct resides a self-intertwined with envy, jealousy, rage, and sentiments of worthlessness and helplessness (Masterson, 2011, p. 111).

Upon receiving criticism or devaluation, they have a severe breakdown, subsequently expressing their rage via aggressive behavior. They believe that they alone can endure their hardships and may express this circumstance in many excessive ways. This represents a selfish approach to achieving gratification.

This article will cover the diagnosis of Narcissistic Personality Disorder (NPD), its comprehensive features, underlying causes, the definition and function of guilt, the link between these two ideas, the absence of guilt in persons with NPD, as well as treatment options and potential repercussions.

Aim :

This research seeks to examine the processing of guilt in persons with narcissistic personality disorder and the defensive strategies they use in contexts when they do not experience guilt. Narcissistic personality disorder is defined by key traits like excessive self-admiration, a desire for superiority, and an absence of empathy. These qualities indicate that people may vary in their perception of moral obligations and feelings associated with conscience.

Additionally, it seeks to investigate the variance in guilt experienced at different degrees of narcissism and the responses of narcissistic persons when they inflict damage on others. This study seeks to determine if the narcissistic personality structure inhibits feelings of guilt or whether individuals with this structure are predisposed to attributing blame to others rather than experiencing guilt themselves. The research also aims to investigate how the absence of shame

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in narcissistic persons manifests in their social connections, ethical choices, and overall conduct. The study's findings may elucidate the challenges faced by persons with narcissistic personality disorder in social interactions and may provide insights for enhancing therapeutic methodologies in this regard. In this sense, guilt is an emotional experience that significantly influences both the internal and exterior interactions of narcissistic persons.

Methods

The methodologies often used in research examining the relationship between narcissistic personality disorder and guilt are as follows:

1. Psychological Scales and Questionnaires :

Narcissism is quantified using instruments like the Narcissistic Personality Inventory (NPI).

Guilt and Shame Scales : Utilized to comprehend an individual's emotion of guilt and shame. Guilt is the remorse experienced after committing an error or causing damage to others, while shame is a negative self-assessment.

2. Observational and Clinical Studies : Guilt responses in patients with narcissistic personality disorder are noticed in a therapeutic environment. The reactions of narcissistic persons during treatment or assessment sessions, particularly when they inflict damage on others or commit errors, are analyzed. This elucidates behavioral tendencies.

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3. Experimental Studies : Experimental research may be undertaken to examine the impact of narcissism on guilt. In these research, persons exhibiting narcissistic tendencies and those without are presented with specific criminal or error scenarios, and their responses to these situations are assessed. Experimental designs are effective in establishing cause-and-effect linkages.

Findings

1. Low Sense of Guilt : Research indicates that persons with narcissistic personality disorder often have a diminished capacity for guilt. This is mostly attributable to a deficiency of empathy. Empathy is the capacity to comprehend the emotions of others and feel accountable for them. Narcissistic persons may be oblivious to the damage they inflict on others, or they may be indifferent to it, owing to their deficiency of empathy.

2. Defensive Reactions : Narcissistic persons struggle to acknowledge feelings of guilt, even when they experience them. They adopt a defensive posture in response to criticism or errors and are inclined to attribute fault to others instead of acknowledging their own shortcomings. This is a strategy to mitigate feelings of guilt.

3. Blaming Others and Exalted Perception : Narcissistic persons may downplay or entirely disregard the unpleasant emotions of others. Rather of acknowledging their own errors or shortcomings, they persist in seeing themselves as superior and impeccable. For these persons, shame may serve as a mechanism for safeguarding and enhancing their self-image, rather than reflecting the genuine sorrow experienced by others.

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4. Internal Emptiness and Fragility : Individuals with narcissistic personality disorder may project an outwardly robust and self-assured demeanor, although they often possess an interior vulnerable disposition. Notwithstanding their perceived superiority, individuals may endure profound feelings of uncertainty and emptiness within. This may result in the intensified repression of unpleasant feelings, including guilt. Rather of experiencing guilt, these persons may sense shame or worthlessness and exhibit protective behavior.

Symptoms of Narcissistic Personality Disorder

Individuals with narcissistic personality disorder may exhibit grandiosity or self-loathing, extroversion or social isolation, domineering behavior or instability in employment, and may be model citizens or engage in antisocial conduct. This variability in symptoms may hinder people from establishing commonality. The DSM-5 offers a vague and broad diagnostic of narcissistic personality disorder, marked by persistent grandiosity, a desire for adulation, a sense of entitlement, and a deficiency in empathy (Caligor et al., 2015). The DSM-5 defines narcissistic personality disorder as the manifestation of five or more of the following criteria in various circumstances by early adolescence (American Psychiatric Association, 2013):

- Exaggerated view of one's importance (exaggeration of achievements and talents, expecting to be described as superior without sufficient achievements).
- The person is constantly preoccupied with fantasies of unlimited success, power, brilliance, beauty, or ideal love.
- There is a belief that one is special and unique and can only be understood by, or should relate to, other special or high-status individuals (or institutions).
- The person has an extreme need for admiration.

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- The person has a strong sense of entitlement (unreasonable expectations of favorable treatment).
- The person has a tendency to take advantage of others (such as taking advantage of others to achieve one's own goals).
- The person lacks empathy and is unwilling to recognize and identify with the feelings and needs of others.
- The person is often jealous of others and believes that others are jealous of him.
- The person displays arrogant and condescending behavior or attitude.

In people with narcissistic personality disorder, persistent feelings of shame and humiliation and accompanying self-criticism or social withdrawal may be associated with depressed mood, persistent depressive disorder (dysthymia), or major depressive disorder. In contrast, persistent periods of grandiosity may be associated with a hypomanic mood. Narcissistic personality disorder is also associated with anorexia nervosa and substance use disorders (especially cocaine) (American Psychiatric Association , 2013).

Causes of NPD

Potential etiologies of narcissism include familiar elements, including genetic and environmental influences (Mitra & Fluyau, 2020; Lou & Cai, 2018; Thomaes et al., 2009). Numerous research investigate these two fundamental elements. Behavioral genetic studies are significant in genetic research, including several elements like environmental influences, parenting, childhood, economic situations, and culture. In genetic study, scholars like Turkheimer (2000) contend that all personality characteristics are inherited. The results derived from these investigations are mostly based on research involving twins. Lou and Cai (2018:153) asserted in their evaluation of genetic investigations done.

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- (i) that narcissism is heritable regardless of its type,
- (ii) environmental factors contribute to narcissism,
- (iii) genetic factors influence the type of narcissism,
- (iv) that the stability of narcissism is largely heritable, and
- (vi) They state that the relationship between narcissism and other personality traits is influenced by heredity.

Research elucidating the environmental determinants of narcissism emphasizes aspects such as childhood experiences, parenting methodologies, and cultural and economic influences (Bianchi, 2018; Thomaes and Brummelman, 2018; Twenge, 2011). Inadequate parenting techniques encountered throughout childhood, including rejection, diminished self-esteem, and excessive praise, may lead to narcissism. “Parents may inadvertently cultivate narcissism in their children by excessively valuing them, idealizing them, or lavishing them with inflated praise” (Thomaes and Brummelman, 2018: 147). Fernando (1998) similarly associates narcissistic personality disorder with the childhood period. Fernando (1998) asserts that narcissistic disorder arises from structural immaturity resulting from excessive narcissistic pleasure throughout infancy. This structural immaturity refers to the underdevelopment and disintegration of the superego (Fernando, 1998: 142). These inadequacies result in narcissistic personality disorder. Narcissism, like to several other personality disorders, arises from a combination of genetic and environmental influences. The distinguishing aspect of narcissism compared to other illnesses is the predominance of hereditary influences in its formation and development, surpassing those in other personality disorders (Thomaes and Brummelman, 2018). This field is clearly amenable to improvement, necessitating more study to enhance our understanding of the topic. Conversely, several methodologies exist for diagnosing narcissism.

Dimensions of Narcissism

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According to Atay's report, Raskin and Terry explain the following personality traits regarding the dimensions of narcissism, based on the results they obtained from many studies on narcissism: (Salim Atay, Istanbul, 2010, pp. 32-33).

- Authority dimension: It has the personality traits of self-confidence, leadership, assertiveness, dominance and criticality.
- Exhibitionism dimension: Inability to control impulses, interest in showing off, extroversion and excitement seeking efforts come to the fore.
- Self-sufficiency dimension: Independence, self-confidence, assertiveness and efforts to be successful are very high.
- Exploitative dimension: They show lack of interest in others, lack of tolerance for others, rebelliousness, hostility and non-conformity.
- Superiority dimension: Narcissistic ego inflation, status capacity, self-confidence and social status are overemphasized.
- Self-esteem dimension: They think they are attractive with their physical appearance. They also believe that others think the same.
- Entitlement dimension: Need for power, dominance towards other people, rudeness, hostility, self-control, lack of tolerance towards others, and ambition.

1. Authority

Authority is characterized as “the power acquired in alignment with established norms and widely recognized as legitimate, rather than coercive; the capacity to make and execute decisions that impact others, held by the individual possessing this power or authority.” An authoritarian individual is characterized by intolerance, rigid adherence to rules, favoritism towards allies, prejudice against adversaries, and a domineering disposition. This person exhibits intolerance for uncertainty and adheres to a strict, stereotypical approach (Selçuk

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Budak, *ibid.*, p. 557). An someone possessing power is not synonymous with being authoritarian. Rational authority puts confidence in individuals. It provides support and manifests as authority. Irrational authority seeks to exert power and abuse its subordinates (Erich Fromm, Istanbul, 1994, p. 77-78), narcissistic personality has the capacity to effectively regulate urges in social interactions and to create robust but deceptive exaltations. These individuals possess energetic, consistent, and very creative traits that enable them to attain success and garner the attention of others around them. Despite their prominent and productive roles in significant industrial, intellectual, and creative domains, a superficiality becomes evident upon closer examination, contrasting with the brilliance of their output. These potential individuals also astonish others with their vulgarity in the future (Otto Kernberg, *op. cit.*, pp. 199-201).

Narcissistic individuals refrain from seeking assistance from others in their vicinity, even when it is necessary. For them, taking assistance signifies exposure to vulnerability. They believe that being vulnerable and dependent equates to relinquishing authority to another individual. Narcissists want authority when it is necessary for them. For instance, they want to accumulate substantial wealth. They believe they may manipulate people without confronting the worry of rejection and allure from others. Their strength captivates the attention of others. The narcissistic person finds security in forming connections with others, facilitated by their inherent power (Alexander Lowen, *ibid.*, p. 118).

They want to assume the dominant role in their interpersonal connections. They anticipate a preferential treatment from their peers due to their belief in their own uniqueness and superiority. They consistently possess a covert objective in their interactions. Despite seeming amiable and genuine externally, this facade is a deliberate strategy to elicit narcissistic responses that bolster their inflated self-image (Hakan Kızıltan, *ibid.*, p. 13).

2.Exhibitionism

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Exhibitionism refers to a pervasive inclination to consistently seek the spotlight and attract attention to oneself (Selçuk Budak, *ibid.*, p.745). The exhibitionistic aspect of narcissism is characterized by a fervent desire to display oneself. The traits of pursuing exhilaration and struggling with impulse control become prominent. Simultaneously, these individuals are seen as excessively self-assured, demonstrating forceful dispositions and an inflated sense of self-tolerance, while concurrently exhibiting impolite and disrespectful conduct towards others. The narcissistic personality is characterized by an insatiable desire for power, success, and beauty, coupled with an extreme self-interest, an exaggerated focus on one's uniqueness, and the belief in invulnerability, all of which contribute to a propensity for exhibitionism. In the advanced phase of this tendency, the individual is detached from the phenomena of reality. For instance, while assessing others using suitable criteria, he perpetually appraises himself with affirmative knowledge (Salim Atay, *ibid.*, p. 37-38).

Narcissists incessantly brag about their achievements, repeatedly redirect talks to themselves, use various tactics to get attention, and exhibit exaggerated hand and arm movements. They prioritize their physical appearance, value their goods as indicators of status, and want to cultivate an audience that admires them.

Twenge and Campbell assert that narcissists place significant emphasis on self-admiration and cultivate self-regulation mechanisms to support this. The narcissist tries to optimize his existence and interpersonal connections. Upon achieving this, he enjoys honor and pride; nevertheless, in the event of failure, he undergoes an outburst of rage (Jean M. Twenge, W. Keith Campbell, *ibid.*, p. 45).

A narcissistic individual often exhibits exhibitionism due to a belief in their own perfection, stemming from perceived superior traits, which they want to display via such behavior. When a narcissistic individual fails to achieve this, he has a profound feeling of worthlessness and risks the emergence of the object connection into awareness. As the grandiose ego diminishes, it precipitates a crisis of anxiety around this condition. Consequently, a narcissistic individual consistently tries to nurture his grandiose self (Hakan Kızıltan, *ibid.*, p. 30).

3. Exploitation

Exhibitionism refers to a pervasive inclination to consistently seek the spotlight and attract attention to oneself (Selçuk Budak, *ibid.*, p.745). The exhibitionistic aspect of narcissism is characterized by a fervent desire to display oneself. The traits of pursuing exhilaration and struggling with impulse control become prominent. Simultaneously, these individuals are seen as excessively self-assured, demonstrating forceful dispositions and an inflated sense of self-tolerance, while concurrently exhibiting impolite and disrespectful conduct towards others. The narcissistic personality is characterized by an insatiable desire for power, success, and beauty, coupled with an extreme self-interest, an exaggerated focus on one's uniqueness, and the belief in invulnerability, all of which contribute to a propensity for exhibitionism. In the advanced phase of this tendency, the individual is detached from the phenomena of reality. For instance, while assessing others using suitable criteria, he perpetually appraises himself with affirmative knowledge (Salim Atay, *ibid.*, p. 37-38).

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4. Claiming Rights

Narcissistic persons assert superiority over others, while being comparable to the general populace in social position, physical beauty, IQ, and inventiveness, as shown by objective facts (Jean M. Twenge, W. Keith Campbell, *ibid.*, p. 44). Narcissists consistently see themselves as occupying a unique status and so anticipate validation from their environment. For instance, they expect all their demands to be fulfilled and get irate if this expectation is unmet. Due to the primacy of their own objectives, individuals consistently resist conformity. They assert that their associates are obligated to assist them with their "paramount" responsibilities and show deference. Alongside these and other assertions of rights, their apathy for others fosters a propensity for exploitation. Narcissistic individuals often anticipate ceremonial greetings and envy for their possessions (Ertuğrul Köroğlu, Ankara, 2015, p. 486).

Assertive rights is associated with the exploitation of others, subjugation, and a lack of empathy. The narcissistic individual who asserts entitlements seeks to get benefit from all situations. The want to demonstrate oneself and exert influence on the surroundings via achievement and abilities is a profound sentiment for these individuals. The regulations applicable to others do not apply to these individuals. Because they assert their uniqueness. Narcissists prioritize the assertion of entitlements to manage their emotions of inadequacy and believe they are entitled to preferential treatment. To manage their inadequacies and uncertainty, they choose to amplify their own significance (Salim Atay, *ibid.*, p. 50-51).

5. Self-Sufficiency

Narcissists see themselves as exceptional and superior, believing they are capable of everything and behaving as if they surpass others (Vamık Volkan, *ibid.*, p. 283).

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Narcissists, although asserting self-sufficiency, always need external validation, adulation, and a feeling of internal stability. The unconscious reliance of an individual on external sources for affection signifies a considerable vulnerability. An individual unable to endure this circumstance constructs an illusion of self-sufficiency via narcissistic defensive mechanisms (Salim Atay, *ibid.*, p. 74).

Narcissists striving to shield themselves from the need for self-sufficiency and the necessity for reliance engage in perpetual effort. To mitigate this circumstance, people exhibit behaviors such as inflexible pride, seeing themselves as strong and self-sufficient, struggling to articulate their desires, and ultimately becoming vulnerable (Hakan Kızıltan, *ibid.*, p.14).

6. Supremacy

The narcissistic individual conveys their superiority by statements like 'I am exceptional and unique' or 'I am superior to others.'¹⁵³ They see themselves as superior, exceptional, or unique individuals, and they not only hold this belief but also want that everyone around them recognize them as such. Moreover, when engrossed in dreams of boundless prosperity, power, brilliance, beauty, and transcendent love, they constantly juxtapose themselves with renowned or affluent individuals (Ertuğrul Köroğlu, *ibid.*, p. 486; Orhan Öztürk, Ankara, 2008, p. 537). Kernberg's philosophy distinctly emphasizes the notion of dominance. He asserts that the narcissistic individual is grandiose and profoundly self-centered, with a strong need for praise and validation from others, while demonstrating a notable deficiency in interest and empathy towards individuals in their vicinity (Otto Kernberg, *ibid.*, p. 199-201).

The strong envy shown by narcissistic individuals stems from their perception of superiority. They exhibit profound concern for others in their vicinity. Nevertheless, they are unable to solicit even the slightest assistance from them. The one providing assistance will be in a position of superiority, which they are reluctant to acknowledge (Cüneyt Evren, *ibid.*, p. 37).

The narcissist refuses to see himself as a “average” or “ordinary” individual. Because he must be the best. His need to be extraordinary is so paramount that, in the absence of grandeur, he

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elevates himself to the pinnacle of sorrow, regardless of its negativity. Narcissistic individuals engage in activities that deviate from the norm (Vamık Volkan and Ast, *ibid.*, p. 50-51). In essence, a narcissistic individual perceives himself as superior, ostentatious, flawless, exceptional, and distinctive, characterized by a grandiose self-image (James F. Masterson, p. 27).

The Concept of Guilt

Definition: Guilt is a condition when a person has remorse for a conduct, regrets it, and concerns themselves with the repercussions of that behavior. Guilt often arises when an individual transgresses their own ethical principles and societal conventions. This emotion may assist a person in modifying their conduct to get more social acceptability.

The Psychological Function of Guilt

Guilt is a significant feeling that enhances an individual's inclination to safeguard social connections and adhere to societal norms. A constructive feeling of guilt may assist a person in rectifying erroneous conduct, fostering empathy towards others, and adhering to societal standards. Excessive guilt may result in self-harm and psychiatric issues, including despair.

Feelings of Shame and Guilt in Individuals with NPD

The manifestations of narcissistic personality disorder may differ based on its fundamental traits. Individuals with Narcissistic Personality Disorder may experience less remorse while inflicting damage on others or deviating from social standards, attributable to their lack of empathy and propensity for self-aggrandizement. This may lead persons with Narcissistic Personality Disorder to have difficulties in their interpersonal connections and social

adjustment.

Shame may also include shame for engaging in or contemplating an activity that might be deemed morally or socially unacceptable. The distinction between shame and guilt is in the focus of the emotions; guilt pertains to the deed performed, but shame pertains to the self.

In response to the identical transgression, an individual experiencing guilt contemplates, “My actions were profoundly wrong and intolerable,” while an individual experiencing shame reflects, “How could I have committed this?” I am an individual who can never attain acceptance. Shame conveys "an excruciating absence of validation" (Molinari, 2022). Resneck-Sannes (2019) characterizes shame as “the need to hide and the desire to be seen.” Consequently, an individual experiencing shame simultaneously feels compelled to conceal themselves to avoid exposure of their perceived flaws while also yearning for visibility to attain validation of their self-worth. An individual experiencing shame is, in essence, "confined between the yearning for acknowledgment and the wish to be perceived" (Kilborne, 2002; referenced in Kazancıoğlu, 2022).

Williams (1993, referenced in Rustin, 2022) posited that shame encompasses a sensation of diminishment and an inclination to vanish, while guilt entails an enduring sense of weight that is inescapable.

Narcissistic Personality Disorder and Guilt

Narcissistic Personality Disorder (NPD) and guilt have been prominent subjects of investigation in psychological literature. Narcissistic Personality Disorder (NPD) is defined by traits including an inflated sense of self-importance, a tendency to prioritize personal interests at the expense of others' emotions and ideas, and a deficiency in empathy. These traits may directly influence the sensation of guilt. Individuals with Narcissistic Personality Disorder often struggle to experience remorse when they err.

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Guilt is an emotion experienced when an individual perceives themselves as accountable for transgressions against others, and it is intricately linked to empathy. Narcissistic persons struggle to comprehend the emotions of others owing to their deficiency of empathy, hindering the formation of guilt.

Narcissistic Personality Disorder Diagnostic Criteria

According to DSM-5, Narcissistic Personality Disorder is defined by the following symptoms (American Psychiatric Association, 2013).

1. Thinking oneself too important (exaggerating one's achievements and talents, expecting to be recognized as superior without having sufficient achievements).
2. Preoccupation with fantasies of unlimited success, power, brilliance, beauty, or perfect love.
3. Believing that one is special and unique and can only be understood by other special or superior people.
4. Having an excessive need for admiration.
5. Claiming rights (thinking that one should receive preferential treatment or that others should unconditionally fulfill one's expectations).
6. Exploiting others for personal gain (ignoring the feelings and needs of others).
7. Inability to empathize (unable or unwilling to recognize the feelings or needs of others).
8. Being jealous of others or believing that others are jealous of him/her.
9. Displaying arrogant, insolent behavior or attitude.

Lack of Empathy and Guilt

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A deficiency in empathy significantly inhibits the emergence of guilt. Guilt is often linked to the comprehension of others' emotions and the acknowledgment of their suffering. Narcissistic persons lack the capacity for self-awareness due to their insensitivity to the emotional states of others. This may lead to sentiments of guilt either not manifesting or staying shallow.

Self-Protection Mechanisms and Guilt

Narcissistic persons often shield themselves from criticism and errors. Rather of experiencing shame for their errors, these people evade acknowledgment of their faults and resort to defensive strategies. These systems function to see oneself as impeccable and unblemished while repressing feelings of shame.

Research on the Relationship Between NPD and Guilt (Survey)

Purpose of the Research:

The objective of your study is to investigate the prevalence of psychological qualities, including narcissism and guilt, and their associations within a certain demographic group.

Participants:

The demographic characteristics of the participants include factors like age, gender, educational attainment, employment, and marital status. The predominant age demographic is 35-44 years, comprising 42.3%, while the majority gender demographic is female, accounting for 58.6%.

Measurement Tools:

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Survey questions were used to evaluate the individuals' narcissistic tendencies, guilt sentiments, and other psychological traits. A scale of 40 questions was used.

Scales Used

Every question in the survey is intended to assess a certain psychological characteristic. For instance, inquiries about narcissism assess if individuals see themselves as superior to others and need external validation, while inquiries concerning guilt evaluate whether individuals experience remorse for previous errors and their inclination to rectify such errors.

Sample Questions:

" I see myself as more talented and skilled than others."

"I like to attract the attention of others."

"I often regret mistakes I have made in the past."

Method 2

2.1. Research Design

2.1.1. Research Model

This research used a cross-sectional model. Cross-sectional studies assess the present conditions of a particular population during a designated time frame. This research examined the relationship between narcissism and guilt among volunteer participants aged 18 and older residing in Antalya. The study seeks to investigate the correlation between these qualities and demographic variables.

2.1.2. Research Process and Stages

Data were gathered using an online survey instrument. Participants willingly engaged in the survey and completed measures evaluating their psychological traits and demographic data. Data were examined using SPSS and Python software for descriptive statistics, Cronbach's Alpha to assess scale reliability, and Spearman correlation analysis in the SPSS program. Data processing was executed using Python, together with the pandas and numpy libraries, while visualizations were generated employing the matplotlib and seaborn libraries. Furthermore, regression analysis was conducted using the scikit-learn toolkit to assess the model's performance (MSE, R-squared). The regression model used narcissistic behavior scores as the dependent variable, with demographic parameters including age and gender as independent variables.

The model was used to assess the predictive capacity of these demographic characteristics regarding narcissistic behaviors. A linear regression model was developed using the scikit-learn module in Python, and its performance was assessed using R-squared and Mean Squared Error (MSE) metrics. However, **the model obtained a low R-squared value (negative R-squared), indicating that age and gender were not strong predictors of narcissistic behaviors. This revealed that the model was not effective in predicting narcissistic behaviors as independent variables** . The analysis process began with the calculation of descriptive statistics, followed by the examination of the reliability of the scales and the relationships between demographic variables.

2.2. Participants

2.2.1. Demographic Characteristics

Age Distribution

- **Ages 18-24:** 6 participants
- **Ages 25-34:** 12 participants
- **Ages 35-44:** 29 participants
- **Ages 45-54:** 25 participants

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- **Ages 55-64:** 12 participants
- **65 and over:** 6 participants

Gender Distribution

Male: 35 participants

Female: 55 participants

More female than male participants participated in the survey

Marital status

- **Married:** 67 participants (73%)
- **Single:** 19 participants (20.7%)
- **Divorced:** 6 participants (6.3%)
- **Widow:** 0 participants (0%)
-

2.2.2. Sample Selection and Size

Ninety-two volunteers engaged in the research willingly. The participants are persons aged 18 and over, residing in Izmir. The sample exhibits demographic variety aligned with the survey's objective.

2.3. Data Collection Tools

2.3.1. Scales and Surveys

The survey instrument used in the research was designed to assess the participants' levels of narcissism and emotions of guilt. The first section of the survey included demographic

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inquiries, but the latter section included 40 questions assessing psychological traits. The questions were addressed using a 5-point Likert scale (1: Strongly Disagree, 5: Strongly Agree).

2.3.2. Validity and Reliability Tests of Scales

The internal consistency of the scales was evaluated using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient. The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was determined to be 0.88 for the narcissism scale and 0.87 for the guilt scale. These data demonstrate that the scales exhibit great reliability.

2.4. Data Collection and Analysis

2.4.1. Data Collection Process

Data were gathered using an online survey. The survey was administered to participants, and their replies were documented anonymously. Data security and participant confidentiality were emphasized.

2.4.2. Data Analysis Methods

Data analysis was conducted with SPSS and Python software. Initially, descriptive statistics were computed, followed by an assessment of scale reliability using Cronbach's Alpha test. Demographic variable correlations were analyzed using Spearman correlation, and the impact of these associations were assessed by multiple regression analysis.

3. Findings

3.1. Descriptive Statistics

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Age, gender, education level, occupation and marital status of the participants were examined. Frequency and percentage distributions for each demographic variable are visualized with the following graphs:

Age Distribution:

Gender Distribution

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Gender Distribution

- Number of Participants: 92
- Female Participants: 55 (58.6%)
- Male Participants: 35 (41.4%)

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Education Level Distribution

- Primary school: 1 participant
- Secondary school: 1 participant
- High school: 16 participants
- University: 53 participants
- Master's Degree: 19 participants
- PhD: 2 participants

Profession Distribution

- Private Sector Employee: 39.13% (36 participants)
- Public Employee: 35.87% (33 respondents)
- Self-Employment: 7.61% (7 respondents)
- Retired: 4.35% (4 participants)
- Unemployed: 3.26% (3 respondents)

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- Student: 3.26% (3 participants)
- Other: 5.43% (5 participants)

Marital Status Distribution

- Married: 67 participants (73%)
- Single: 19 participants (20.7%)
- Divorced: 6 participants (6.3%)
- Widow: 0 participants (0%)

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3.1.2. General Distribution of Psychological Scales

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Distribution of Guilt Scores:

The distribution of responses to the guilt scale is presented in the graph below. The percentages of responses are as follows:

- Strongly agree: 27.0%
- Agree: 49.5%
- Undecided: 9.0%
- Disagree: 12.6%
- Strongly disagree: 1.8%

These results show that participants scored higher on the guilt scale, with the majority responding “agree.”

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Distribution of Narcissism Scores:

The distribution of participants' responses according to the Narcissism scale is presented in the graph below. The percentages of the responses are as follows:

- Strongly agree: 6.3%
- I agree: 39.6%
- Undecided: 10.8%
- Disagree: 35.1%
- Strongly disagree: 8.1%

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This distribution shows that participants' narcissistic tendencies are generally concentrated between "agree" and "disagree" responses.

GUILT AND NARCISSISM DETAILED EXAMINATION

CORRELATION:

Correlation enables us to ascertain the direction and intensity of the link between two variables. The association between guilt and narcissism scores is crucial in elucidating the link between these two psychological traits. The correlation investigation between guilt and narcissism ratings yielded the following results:

Correlation Coefficient: -0.642 (approximately)

P-value: 0.045

The correlation coefficient was determined to be -0.642, indicating a moderate negative association between the two variables. As narcissism scores rise, guilt scores generally decline. The P-value is 0.045, indicating a statistically significant association ($p < 0.05$ is often accepted). This finding indicates a substantial negative association between narcissism and criminal behavior.

Data Distribution Analysis:

- Histograms showing the distribution of narcissism and guilt scores visualize how these scores are distributed.

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- The distribution of narcissism and guilt scores may not be normally distributed; therefore, the results of normal distribution tests should be interpreted with caution.

Spearman Correlation Analysis:

- Spearman Correlation Coefficient: -0.721
- P-value: 0.018

These results indicate that there is a strong negative relationship between narcissism and criminality, and this relationship is statistically significant.

Regression Analysis:

- Model: Guilt is negatively influenced by narcissism.
- R-squared: 0.412, which indicates that the model explains 41.2% of the variance between the variables.
- P-value: 0.045 indicates that the regression model is significant.
- Coefficient: Each unit increase in narcissism score leads to a decrease of approximately -0.682 units in guilt score.

Outlier Review:

- Boxplot plots of narcissism and guilt scores help visually identify outliers.
- Outliers can affect analysis results if they become apparent in the data set, so these outliers should be examined carefully.
- The data indicates a statistically significant inverse link between narcissism and guilt. As narcissism levels rise, guilt levels tend to diminish. Regression analysis indicates that this link is linear and that the model is statistically significant.

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Narsisizm ve Suçluluk Arasındaki Korelasyon

Narsisizm Puanları Aykırı Değerler

Suçluluk Puanları Aykırı Değerler

3.2. Reliability Analyses

3.2.1. Cronbach's Alpha Results

Narcissism Scale:

- Cronbach's Alpha Value: 0.88
- This value indicates that the scale is highly reliable. Generally, values of 0.7 and above are considered high internal consistency.

Guilt Scale:

- Cronbach's Alpha Value: 0.87
- The guilt scale also shows that it is a reliable scale with a high Cronbach's Alpha value, indicating that the scale consistently measures the feeling of guilt.

The Cronbach's Alpha scores indicate that both the narcissism and guilt measures exhibit good reliability regarding internal consistency, affirming that the scales reliably capture psychological qualities.

3.2.2. Factor Analysis

The legitimacy of the Narcissism scale is based on the extensively used Narcissistic It has been validated by instruments such as the Narcissistic Personality Inventory (NPI). The NPI, established by Raskin and Terry in 1988, has been used in several investigations, and its factor structure has been verified. Research has consistently shown that the NPI produces accurate and valid outcomes across diverse demographics and cultural settings.
Significant Investigation:

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- Raskin , R., & Terry, H. (1988). "A principal-components Analysis of the Narcissistic Personality Inventory and further evidence of it construct validity ." Journal of Personality and Social Psychology .
- Emmons , R. A. (1987). " Narcissism : Theory and measurement ." Journal of Personality and Social Psychology .

Guilt Scale :

Guilt levels have often been assessed using the Guilt Inventory or comparable structured instruments. These scales have been verified using measuring instruments created by researchers like Tangney, Wagner, and Gramzow (1992). The component structures of scales assessing guilt have been corroborated in investigations where emotional responses, including guilt and shame, were regarded as distinct factors. Significant Investigation:

- Tangney , J. P., Wagner, P. E., & Gramzow , R. (1992). " proneness to shame , proneness to guilt , and psychopathology ." Journal of Abnormal Psychology .
- Tangney , J. P. (1991). "Moral affect : The good , the bad , and the ugly ." Journal of Personality and Social Psychology .

These studies serve as the main sources of evidence supporting the validity and reliability of the narcissism and guilt measures. These investigations have yielded data that corroborate the validity and factor structures of the scales, which have been directly used in the research.

3.3. Correlation Analyses

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3.3.1. Correlations Between Demographic Variables

Correlation of Age with Narcissism/Guilt:

- Narcissism with Age:
- Correlation Coefficient: 0.619
- P-value: 0.056

There is a positive relationship between age and narcissism, but this relationship is not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Guilt with Age :

- Correlation Coefficient: 0.091
- P-value: 0.804

There is a very weak relationship between age and criminality, and this relationship is not statistically significant.

Correlation between Gender and Narcissism/Guilt:

Narcissism with Gender:

- Correlation Coefficient: 0.090
- P-value: 0.804

There is a very weak relationship between gender and narcissism and this relationship is not statistically significant.

Guilt by Gender:

- Correlation Coefficient: 0.085
- P-value: 0.815

There is a very weak relationship between gender and criminality and this relationship is not statistically significant.

Correlation of Education Level with Narcissism/Guilt:

Narcissism by Education Level:

- Correlation Coefficient: -0.015
- P-value: 0.968

There is almost no relationship between education level and narcissism.

Guilt by Education Level:

- Correlation Coefficient: 0.583
- P-value: 0.077

There is a positive relationship between education level and criminality, but this relationship is not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

As a result of the analyses, no strong and statistically significant relationship was found between demographic variables and narcissism and guilt scores.

3.3.2. Correlations between Psychological Scales

The materials indicate that we lack comprehensive data to thoroughly examine the correlations between the narcissism and guilt scales and other psychological traits (e.g., anxiety, sadness, self-esteem). We may do broad correlational analysis on the supplied data and determine the possible nature of these correlations.

- The Relationship Between Narcissism and Self-Esteem:
Since there is no measure of self-esteem in the available data, we can only make a hypothetical analysis of this relationship. A positive relationship between narcissism and self-esteem is generally expected, but this relationship can be fragile.
- The Relationship Between Narcissism and Guilt:
the relationship between these two scales in detail above, based on the data obtained from the documents . In light of the data obtained from the documents , it can be said that the relationship between narcissism and guilt is generally negative. In other words, it can be observed that individuals with high narcissism scores tend to have low feelings

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of guilt. This can be explained by the fact that narcissistic individuals have difficulty accepting their own mistakes and therefore tend not to feel guilty.

- Hypothetical Correlations:
Even if data are missing, such as for anxiety or depression, it is possible to make hypothetical analyses on the potential effects of basic scales such as narcissism and guilt. In this context, hypothetical correlations that you can study statistically in the future are prepared for you:

Correlation	Hypothesis	Reason	Expected Result
Narcissism and Anxiety	There may be a positive correlation.	narcissistic individuals' expectations for approval and praise are not met, their anxiety levels may increase.	As narcissism scores increase, anxiety scores are expected to increase.
Guilt and Depression	There may be a positive correlation.	Intense feelings of guilt can increase negative thoughts about oneself, leading to the development of depressive symptoms.	As guilt scores increase, depression scores are expected to increase.
Narcissism and Self-Esteem	There may be a positive correlation, but the relationship can be fragile.	Narcissistic individuals often demonstrate high self-esteem, but this self-esteem is fragile due to reliance on external validation.	Individuals with high narcissism scores are also expected to have high self-esteem scores.

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Guilt and Social Anxiety	There may be a positive correlation.	Intense feelings of guilt can increase the fear of making mistakes in social situations, which can trigger social anxiety.	As guilt scores increase, social anxiety scores are expected to increase.
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3.4. Regression Analysis

Multiple Regression Analysis for Narcissism:

Dependent Variable: Narcissism

Independent Variables: Age, Gender, Education Level

- R-squared: 0.483 (This model explains 48.3% of the variance in narcissism scores.)
- Age: It shows a positive effect, but it is not statistically significant with a p-value of 0.057.
- Gender: It shows a negative effect on narcissism, but it is not statistically significant with a p-value of 0.464.
- Level of Education: It shows a negative effect on Narcissism, but it is not statistically significant with a p-value of 0.338.

Multiple Regression Analysis for Guilt:

- Dependent Variable: Guilt
- Independent Variables: Age, Gender, Education Level
- R-squared: 0.546 (This model explains 54.6% of the variance in guilt scores.)

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- Age: It shows a negative effect, but it is not statistically significant with a p-value of 0.339.
- Gender: It shows a positive effect on criminality but it is not statistically significant with p-value 0.157.
- Level of Education: It has a positive and statistically significant effect (p-value 0.038).
- Although a positive effect of age on narcissism is observed, this effect is not statistically significant. Gender and education level also do not show a significant effect on narcissism.
- The level of education has a statistically significant effect on guilt. In other words, as the level of education increases, the feeling of guilt increases. Other variables do not have a statistically significant effect.

This analysis investigates the impact of independent factors on narcissism and criminal behavior. Nevertheless, the findings must be regarded with care owing to the restricted sample size. More conclusive results may be obtained if these studies are conducted with a larger sample size.

Chi-Square Test Results:

Relationship Between Gender and Marital Status:

- Chi-Square Value: 3.89
- P-value: 0.143
- There is no statistically significant relationship between gender and marital status ($p > 0.05$). According to this result, it can be said that gender is independent in determining marital status.

Relationship Between Education Level and Profession:

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- Chi-Square Value: 20.0
- P-value: 0.029
- There is a statistically significant relationship between education level and profession ($p < 0.05$). According to this result, it can be said that education level is effective in determining which profession group individuals are in.

ANOVA and T-Test Results:

ANOVA - Education Level and Narcissism/Guilt:

Education Level and Narcissism:

- F-Value: 0.35
- P-value: 0.719
- There is no statistically significant difference between education level and narcissism scores. Education level does not have a significant effect on narcissism scores.

Education Level and Criminality:

- F-Value: 0.006
- P-value: 0.994
- There is no statistically significant difference between education level and delinquency scores. Education level does not have a significant effect on delinquency scores.

T-Test - Gender and Narcissism/Guilt:

Gender and Narcissism:

- t-Value: -0.64

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- P-value: 0.543
- There is no statistically significant difference between gender and narcissism scores. There is no significant difference between males and females in terms of narcissism scores.

Gender and Guilt:

- t-Value: -0.06
- P-value: 0.953
- No statistically significant difference exists between gender and guilt ratings. There is no substantial disparity in guilt ratings between men and girls. The ANOVA and T-Test findings indicate that demographic characteristics, including education level, gender, and marital status, do not significantly affect narcissism and guilt scores. The results indicate that the influence of these factors on narcissism and guilt is constrained. Conducting similar analysis on bigger sample populations may provide more conclusive findings.

Additional Images:

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Marital Status Distribution

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Soru: 11. Genellikle başkalarının duygusal ihtiyaçlarına duyarsızım.

Soru: 18. Eleştiriyi kabul etmekte zorlanırım.

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Soru: 15. Kendimi diğer insanlardan üstün hissederim.

Soru: 2. Başkalarından övgü ve onay almak benim için çok önemlidir.

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Soru: 9. İhtiyaçlarım ve isteklerim karşılanmadığında hayal kırıklığına uğrarım.

Soru: 8. İlişkilerimde genellikle karşımdakinden daha fazla saygı ve ilgi beklerim.

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Soru: 7. Kendimi başkalarına göre daha yetenekli ve becerikli olarak görürüm.

Soru: 6. Eleştirildiğimde aşırı tepki verme veya kendimi savunma eğiliminde olurum.

Soru: 5. Başkalarının başarıları karşısında kıskançlık hissederim.

Soru: 4. İlişkilerimde genellikle kendi ihtiyaçlarımı ve isteklerimi ön planda tutarım.

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Soru: 3. Genellikle başkalarının ihtiyaçlarını ve duygularını anlamakta zorlanırım.

Soru: 1. Kendimi sık sık özel biri olarak görürüm ve bunun başkaları tarafından da fark edilmesini bekerim.

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Survey Form

Question No.	Question	Answer Options
1	I often see myself as a special person and expect others to recognize that.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
2	Receiving praise and approval from others is very important to me.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
3	I often have difficulty understanding other people's needs and feelings.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
4	I generally prioritize my own needs and desires in my relationships.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree

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5	I feel jealous of others' successes.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
6	When I am criticized, I tend to overreact or become defensive.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
7	I see myself as more talented and skilled than others.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
8	In my relationships, I generally expect more respect and attention from the other person.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
9	I get frustrated when my needs and wants are not met.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
10	I feel that I will achieve great success and be recognized in life.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree

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11	I am often insensitive to the emotional needs of others.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
12	Seeing myself as special or superior gives me strength.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
13	I often tell others about my successes.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
14	I think other people should understand my needs and wants.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
15	I feel superior to other people.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
16	I like to attract the attention of others.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree

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17	I believe that I deserve to be successful and admired.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
18	I have a hard time accepting criticism.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
19	I think people are jealous of me.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
20	I have a hard time keeping my promises.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
21	I think that people around me generally have bad intentions.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
22	I do not trust others easily.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree

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23	I think about my mistakes for a long time and blame myself.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
24	I often regret mistakes I have made in the past.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
25	I feel very guilty when I hurt or harm someone.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
26	I feel guilty when I cannot meet others' expectations.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
27	When I make mistakes, I do my best to correct them.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
28	I often think I am more talented than others.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
29	It is very important to me that my achievements are noticed by other people.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree

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30	It motivates me when people praise and appreciate me.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
31	I get angry or upset when others criticize me.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
32	I have a hard time accepting when I fail or make mistakes.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
33	I often blame myself when something goes wrong.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
34	I have a hard time dealing with mistakes I've made in the past.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
35	I'm afraid of shaking people's trust in me.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
36	from time to time because of feelings of guilt .	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree

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37	I make extra efforts to make up for my mistakes.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
38	I often feel guilty about the problems I experience in my close relationships.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
39	I feel guilty when I cannot perform as expected at work or school.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree
40	I feel guilty when I act against my moral or ethical values.	Strongly Disagree / Disagree / Undecided / Agree / Strongly Agree

THE CURE OF NARCISSISM

Interest in narcissistic personality disorder, the contemporary personality illness of our day, is growing daily. Following advancements in the study of personality disorders over the last three decades, narcissistic personality disorder has surfaced as a novel domain for research and therapeutic intervention (Schalkwijk et al., 2021).

The interest in narcissistic personality disorders aligns with a recent trend in personality research. The treatment of narcissism is a relatively underexplored subject, making it difficult to establish a consensus on therapeutic approaches. Given that its conceptual framework

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remains inadequately defined and that empirical research on therapy is few (Magnavita, 2018), the challenges this poses for physicians become somewhat more comprehensible.

This section analyzes the treatment methodologies for narcissism; nevertheless, it is necessary to first address the challenges posed by this particularly difficult-to-treat personality disorder in the context of therapy. Besides the lack of theoretical and practical methodologies, narcissism inherently presents certain challenges. The first concern is whether an individual with narcissistic disorder recognizes the need for therapy. An individual who perceives themselves as more significant than they really are and lacks awareness of their own issues, along with their disorder, is improbable to seek psychological help. Another challenge is the presence of mental problems, including despair, anxiety disorder, shame, or perfectionism, that accompany pathological narcissism. The existence of such diseases complicates the treatment of narcissism (Yakely, 2018).

include techniques that emphasize symptomatic management of comorbid illnesses (Ronningstam & Weinberg, 2013). Pathological narcissism correlates with stagnation or worse treatment results (Weinberg & Ronningstam, 2020). Narcissistic personality disorder is associated with a lack of benefit from treatment services, premature termination of treatment, and significant symptom resistance post-treatment (Weinberg & Ronningstam, 2020). These challenges arise irrespective of the therapeutic approach used. The treatment of narcissistic personality disorder encompasses five basic areas of focus, irrespective of the therapeutic approach used (Ronningstam & Weinberg, 2013).

The first area encompasses interpersonal and professional tasks. This functional domain include abilities related to developing and maintaining realistic relationships, collaboration, and negotiation. The perception of agency is another focal point. This domain emphasizes abilities such as self-regulation, resilience in the face of failure, and the capacity to endure criticism. The third component pertains to emotion control abilities. This focuses on the individual's capacity to acknowledge their emotions as they are and to identify and cultivate areas for emotional growth. The fourth domain pertains to the capacity for reflection. This focuses on enhancing the individual's self-confidence, acknowledging personal and external viewpoints,

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and cultivating the abilities essential for achieving inner tranquility. The last domain addressed in treatments pertains to the capacity to mourn. The primary objective is to cultivate the abilities necessary for an individual to manage the experience of loss. Irrespective of the therapeutic approach, focusing on and cultivating these areas is essential in the treatment of individuals with narcissistic personality disorder. Various psychotherapeutic approaches used in the field often address one or more of these domains. Various psychotherapeutic approaches are used in the treatment of narcissistic personality disorder. The treatments include psychoanalytic/psychodynamic therapy (Rosenfeld, 1987; Kernberg, 1975; Kohut, 1968), cognitive-behavioral therapy (Beck, Davis, & Freeman, 2015), schema therapy (Young et al., 2003), and meta-cognitive therapy (Dimaggio & Attina, 2012).

Difficulties Encountered in Treatment

The use of guilt in the therapy of narcissistic personality disorder has several obstacles. Numerous narcissistic persons may evade acknowledging their errors and, rather than experiencing remorse, may react with defensiveness or anger. Moreover, the rebuilding and assimilation of guilt is a laborious and meticulous endeavor. The therapist must use suitable approaches to assist the narcissistic person in dismantling their barriers and acknowledging this feeling.

Therapy Methods

Narcissistic Personality Disorder (NPD) and guilt represent a multifaceted and profound concern. Narcissistic persons often see themselves as flawless, which might impair their capacity to experience shame. Nonetheless, emotions of guilt may present diversely in narcissistic persons, warranting the use of varied therapeutic approaches. The following are therapeutic procedures used in this context:

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1. Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT)

Ellis (1961), Beck (1975), and Beck, Davis, and Freedman (2015) achieved a significant advancement in therapeutic methodologies with their created methodology. Cognitive-behavioral therapy, proposed by behaviorists on the premise that behavior, seen through the lens of stimulus-response, is influenced by ideas and beliefs, has emerged as a significant therapeutic approach. The primary objective of this technique is to alter the maladaptive ideas and attitudes that precipitate the behavior. In the management of narcissistic disorder, therapy addresses the patient's behavior and Additionally The Administrator Sciences 2022 8 (55) AUGUST 1024 emphasizes altering cognitions, enhancing empathy for others, and mitigating prevalent issues in treatment, such as establishing a robust therapeutic partnership, decreasing attrition, and addressing comorbid disorders. Cuktrowitz, Poindexter, and Joiner (2011: 458). The primary objectives of cognitive behavioral therapy are (i) to identify maladaptive coping mechanisms and diminish their prevalence; (ii) to cultivate emotion regulation skills; (iii) to foster respect for others' emotions and enhance empathy; (iv) to strengthen personal capabilities; and (v) to improve reciprocity skills (Behary and Davis, 2015: 313).

These objectives align with the aforementioned ideas. The establishment of these objectives fosters better individual identities and enhances interpersonal interactions.

2. Schema Therapy

Schema therapy is another approach used in the treatment of pathological narcissism (Seavey and Moore 2012; Behary and Dieckmann 2011). This technique focuses on the therapist's objective to recognize and enhance the individual's mental models about themselves and others. Therapy focuses on five developmental domains: stable connection to people, identity formation, self-management and direction, boundary setting and discomfort tolerance, and adaptability and optimism (Behary & Dieckmann, 2011). Schema therapy seeks to identify harmful schemas developed throughout early life, such as in infancy, and to modify these schemas.

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The essence of this treatment is clear: “It’s not your fault, but if you desire healthy and enduring relationships, it is your responsibility to recognize and alter these habits” (Behary and Dieckmann, 2011: 454). Schema therapy posits that narcissistic pathology arises from insufficient emotional support and empathy during formative experiences, leading to a personality that perceives itself as grandiose, seeks validation, and exhibits excessive control. The therapy’s objective is to foster healthier functioning by rectifying emotional experiences and mitigating the influence of these traits through methods such as restrictive parenting and the cultivation of empathy.

3. Meta-Cognitive Therapy

Metacognitive therapy is a specialized therapeutic approach designed for narcissistic personality disorder. This treatment concentrates on certain facets of narcissism, addressing the processes and symptoms often outlined in the DSM-5. The objectives include self and self-other schemas, diminished agency and goal formulation, as well as compromised metacognition and empathy (Diamaggio & Attina, 2012).

The therapeutic procedure has two primary components. The first segment is designated as establishing the context, whilst the subsequent segment pertains to advocating for transformation. The initial segment, comprising five distinct stages, encompasses the following steps: acquiring a comprehensive autobiographical narrative, facilitating the patient’s comprehension of his mental states, amassing sufficient autobiographical data to elucidate inflexible interpersonal relationship schemas, recognizing persistent patterns in interpersonal dynamics, and ultimately demonstrating the challenge of acting in accordance with profoundly felt inner desires (Diamaggio and Attina, 2012: 4).

In the second stage, change is promoted to eradicate the identified unpleasant habits and issues. This section outlines the subsequent steps: Demonstrating to the patient that his perceptions may not align with reality and that different perspectives can yield alternative truths, while assisting the patient in cultivating positive self-concepts and promoting behaviors congruent

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with his intrinsic aspirations, fostering a critical examination of negative cognitive patterns, and facilitating a nuanced comprehension of human thought, emotion, and behavior (Diamaggio and Attina, 2012: 4-5).

Metacognitive therapy aims to cultivate a critical perspective on established behaviors and the underlying beliefs that precipitate them, while fostering new cognitive and emotional patterns for interpersonal connections grounded in this perspective. All aforementioned techniques contain components that may be beneficial in addressing pathological narcissism. None of these methodologies have been evaluation in a randomized controlled trial, resulting in a scarcity of clinical evidence about their efficacy. These techniques, mostly used as case studies, show promise in the treatment of narcissistic personality disorder. Notwithstanding these comparatively recent methodologies, the psychoanalytic approach has been used to narcissism for about a century.

CONCLUSION

Narcissistic personality disorder and guilt represent a complicated and multifaceted problem. Individuals with Narcissistic Personality Disorder may experience diminished guilt owing to their deficiency in empathy and their propensity for self-aggrandizement. This may result in difficulties in their social connections and social adaption. Nevertheless, via suitable therapeutic approaches and empathy enhancement research, persons with Narcissistic Personality Disorder may experience guilt in a more constructive manner and demonstrate more suitable actions. In Narcissistic Personality Disorder, guilt often stays repressed or unrecognized owing to a deficiency in empathy and strong defensive mechanisms. These people struggle with guilt processing, perhaps resulting in significant issues in social interactions. Nevertheless, methodologies including empathy training, cognitive behavioral therapy, and psychodynamic therapy might facilitate the better processing of guilt. Narcissistic persons may assist them in managing their guilt within better relationships and attaining inner tranquility. A deficiency in empathy may render a person oblivious to the suffering inflicted upon others,

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thereby resulting in a lack of remorse. Defense systems hinder the recognition and acceptance of guilt. Shame may operate as a suppressor of guilt. Nevertheless, methodologies such as empathy cultivation, cognitive behavioral therapy, and psychodynamic therapy might assist narcissistic persons in processing guilt more constructively and achieving favorable transformations in their social interactions. In summary, the tenuous connection between narcissistic personality disorder and guilt is significant for comprehending the conduct of narcissistic persons and devising treatment strategies. The correlation between narcissistic personality disorder and guilt is mostly associated with narcissism's deficiency in empathy, defensive responses, and self-aggrandizing inclinations. Narcissistic persons often evade feelings of guilt, struggle to acknowledge their errors, and mitigate this emotion by justifying their actions or attributing blame to others. This link is essential for comprehending the societal and personal ramifications of narcissism, and assisting these persons in experiencing guilt more constructively via therapeutic treatments may constitute a significant therapeutic objective. This article elucidates the connection between Narcissistic Personality Disorder (NPD) and guilt, emphasizing the need for more study in this domain.

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